

POSSIBLE EVOLUTIONARY CONNECTION AMONGST THE DIFFERENT TYPES OF SEYFERT GALAXIES

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Abstract

A very large sample of Seyfert galaxies (217,272 galaxies) obtained from SDSS DR10 (Sloan Digital Sky Survey Data Release 10) were used for this study. The accretion rate (\dot{m}) was calculated from the bolometric luminosity (L_{bol}) and velocity dispersion (σ) using this relation: $\log \dot{m} = -36.977 + \log L_{\text{bol}} - 4.02 \log \sigma$ and using the M - σ (M - σ) relation, the mass of the supermassive black hole was estimated as; $M_{\text{BH}} = 10^8 M_{\odot} \times 3.1(\sigma/200\text{kms}^{-1})^4$. These calculated parameters enabled in ascertaining the nature of the different classes of Seyfert galaxies. The results obtained show that, as the black hole mass of an AGN (Seyfert galaxy) increases, there is a decrease in its accretion rate and the region of broad line emission progressively declines from its high intensity in Seyfert 1s to the point of disappearance. Galaxies at their early stage in life are very luminous and accretes matter at a very high rate, but as they get older their luminosities and accretion rate reduce with an associated increment in their black hole masses. And since this can only be achieved with time, I infer that there is a possible evolutionary sequence amongst the Seyfert galaxies in which Seyfert 1 galaxies evolve to Seyfert 2 galaxies.

Keywords: Accretion rate, blackhole mass, Seyfert galaxies, velocity dispersion, emission lines

Introduction

An active galactic nucleus (AGN) is a compact region and very luminous object at the center of a galaxy that has a much higher than normal luminosity over all the electromagnetic spectrum. A galaxy hosting an AGN is called an active galaxy. It is currently believed that the supermassive black hole (SMBH) provides the central power source for the AGN and the high luminosity is derived from energy released by matter accreting onto the SMBH (10^6 to $10^{10} M_{\odot}$) (Kazanas, 2012). AGN are the most powerful, long-lived objects and steady source of luminosity in the universe. They range from nuclei of nearby galaxies emitting about 10^{40} ergs⁻¹ to distant quasars emitting more at about 10^{47} ergs⁻¹ (1 erg = 0.1 μ J) (Matzner, 2001). Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN) can be classified in many ways based on the observed morphologies or properties. Their classifications are not necessarily mutually exclusive, being based on disparate criteria. Some AGNs are classified may be due to; similar evolutionary trend, observed variability of luminosities (Urry & Padovani, 1995), some due to the viewing angle (orientation effect), some may be due to level of toroidal obscuration (Elitzur, 2012), while some others might be as a result of relativistic beaming. Equally, AGN can be classified based on their radio properties into radio-loud and radio-quiet AGNs (Donoso, 2010; Urry & Padovani, 1995). The classification of AGNs may also be based on their observed optical properties as Type I (showing both broad and narrow emission lines) and Type II (showing only narrow emission lines) (Ricci et. al, 2011; Fanaroff & Riley, 1974).

Fig. 1. Classification of AGN sources

Seyfert Galaxies

Seyfert galaxies are a subclass of active galactic nuclei (AGN) and are categorized as low luminosity, radio-quiet AGN, hosted in spiral or lenticular galaxies (Singh et al., 2011). Seyfert galaxies are one of the largest groups of active galaxies, along with quasars. They are very luminous, distant and bright sources of electromagnetic radiation with very high surface brightness whose spectra reveals high ionization emission lines (Peterson, 1997) and their host galaxies are clearly detectable (Maiolino and Rieke, 1995). They have super massive black hole (SMBH) at their centres which are surrounded by accretion discs of in-falling materials. The accretion discs are believed to be the source of the observed ultraviolet (UV) radiation which provides the best diagnostic for the composition of the surrounding material (Davidsen, 1993). It is the active galactic nuclei in Seyfert galaxies that produce the strong radiation which excites gas around the central regions, giving rise to the observed emission lines (Ridpath, 1997).

Seyfert galaxies are low luminosity active galactic nuclei that have an absolute B-band luminosity of $M_B > -21.51 + 5 \log h_0$ (Schmidt and Green, 1983), with h_0 denoting the Hubble constant in units of $100 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. They were the first type of active galaxy to be discovered (Whittle, 2006). They have similar nucleus like quasars (very luminous, distant and bright sources of electromagnetic radiation) with very high surface brightness whose spectra reveal strong, high-ionization emission lines (Peterson, 1997), but unlike quasars, their host galaxies are clearly detectable (Petrov, 2004; Maiolino & Rieke, 1995). Seyfert galaxies have extremely bright nuclei, with luminosities ranging between 10^8 and 10^{11} solar luminosities. Only about 5% of them are radio bright; their emissions are moderate in gamma rays and bright in X-rays (Peterson, 1997 and Popping, 2008). Their visible and infrared spectra show very bright emission lines of hydrogen, helium, nitrogen, and oxygen (Massi, 2013). These emission lines exhibit strong Doppler broadening, which implies velocities from 500 to 4,000 km s^{-1} and are believed to originate near an accretion disc surrounding the central black hole (Osterbrock & Ferland, 2006).

The common characteristics and efficient ways to detect Seyfert galaxies include; looking specifically for galaxies with bright ultraviolet emission, bright x-ray emission, or unusual far-

infrared colors (Whittle, 2006). Studying Seyfert galaxies in the visible light wave band reveals that most Seyfert galaxies look like normal spiral galaxies, but when studied under other wavelengths, it becomes clear that the luminosity of their cores is of comparable intensity to the luminosity of whole galaxies the size of the Milky Way (Soper, 2013). Over the years, more than 800 Seyfert galaxies have been discovered (Whittle, 2006). In gathering the spectrophotometric data for the Seyfert galaxies, it became obvious that not all spectra from Seyfert galaxies are identical. Seyfert galaxies were therefore classified according to the characteristics of their emission spectra (Goad et. al., 2012). A simple classification into types I and II has been devised, with the classes depending on the relative width of their emission lines (Weedman, 1973).

Seyfert Galaxies Classification

Because Seyfert galaxies are characterized by strong and broad emission lines, the nature of these emission lines was used as the classification criterion. Seyfert galaxies are classified according to the emission lines shown by their spectra as; Seyfert 1 galaxies (S1s) showing both broad and narrow emission lines and Seyfert 2 galaxies (S2s) showing only narrow emission lines (Ricci et. al., 2011). Many Seyfert galaxies exhibit optical spectra with properties in-between those of S1 and S2 (Osterbrock and Koski, 1976). These objects have been classified as type 1.2, 1.5, 1.8 and 1.9 Seyfert galaxies, depending on the details of their optical spectra (Ricci et. al., 2011; Osterbrock and Martel, 1993). The broad-line region (BLR) is posited to originate from UV or X-ray illumination of hydrogen clouds around the accretion disc while the narrow-line region (NLR) is present in all AGN (Villarroel et. al., 2012).

Seyfert 1 Galaxies

Based on our classification (bolometric luminosity, L_{bol}), there is a threshold bolometric luminosity which determines the appearance and disappearance of the broad line region (BLR). This is given by, $L_{bol(threshold)} = 5 \times 10^{39} \mathfrak{m}^{2/3} \text{ ergs}^{-1}$, where $\mathfrak{m} = M_{BH}/10^7 M_{\odot}$, and M_{BH} is the black hole mass of the object and M_{\odot} is the mass of the Sun (Elitzur et. al., 2014). Seyfert galaxies with bolometric luminosities greater than the threshold bolometric luminosity are classified as Seyfert 1s while those less than or equal the threshold bolometric luminosity are the Seyfert 2s. Seyfert 1 galaxies (S1s) are very bright sources of ultraviolet light and X-rays (Bremer, 2014), in addition to the visible light coming from their cores. They have two sets of emission lines on their spectra: narrow emission lines with widths (measured in velocity units) of several hundred kilometers per second, and broad lines with widths up to 10^4 kms^{-1} . The broad emission lines which are indicative of a central concentration of hot gas that is expanding at speeds of up to thousands of kilometers per second (Hodge, 2013), originate above the accretion disc of the super-massive black hole thought to power the galaxy, while the narrow lines occur beyond the broad line region of the accretion disc. Both emissions are caused by heavily ionized gas (Armitage, 2004).

Seyfert 2 Galaxies

Seyfert 2 galaxies (S2s) have a characteristic bright core which also appears bright even when viewed at the infrared wavelengths (Siobahn, 2013). Their spectra contain only narrow emission lines (but still wider than emission lines in normal galaxies), which indicates that they have very low velocities associated with them (Hodge, 2013). In S2s, both permitted and forbidden lines were about equal with velocity ranging up to about 1000 kms^{-1} . These narrow lines are due to low density gas clouds at larger distances (than the broad line clouds) from the nucleus. In Seyfert 2 galaxies, unlike the S1s, their X-ray radiation appears to be absorbed by material in the line of sight (LOS) between the object and the observer (Hodge, 2013).

The Sample

The data used in this study were obtained from SDSS DR10 (Sloan Digital Sky Survey Data Release 10, the paper for it is Ahn et. al. 2013, submitted to APJS and posted at arXiv: 1307.7735). The data consist of 217,272 Seyfert galaxies, with their observed parameters which includes; velocity dispersion, luminosity distance, and equivalent width and flux of hydrogen alpha ($H\alpha$). Based on the flux of hydrogen alpha, the bolometric luminosity (L_{bol}) was calculated and further, the accretion rate was deduced. The black hole mass was calculated from their velocity dispersion using the $M - \sigma$ relationship. The data were classified into Seyfert 1 (188,486 galaxies) and Seyfert 2 (28,786 galaxies) based on their bolometric luminosities; $L_{bol} > L_{bol(threshold)} =$ Seyfert 1s, while $L_{bol} \leq L_{bol(threshold)} =$ Seyfert 2s. The Seyfert 2 galaxies were further classified into hidden broad line (HBLR) and non-hidden broad line (non-HBLR) Seyfert 2 galaxies based on their accretion rate (\dot{m}); $\dot{m} > \dot{m}_{min} =$ HBLR, while $\dot{m} \leq \dot{m}_{min} =$ non-HBLR.

Data Analysis and Discussions

(a). Mass accretion rate: Accretion is the process in which matter under the influence of gravity is attracted to and increases the mass of a celestial object. The matter usually forms an accretion disc around the accreting object. The rate at which matter accretes into the black hole of a given object is proportional to its bolometric luminosity and the velocity dispersion of the object. Following Laor (2003), the accretion rate (\dot{m}) can be calculated from the bolometric luminosity (L_{bol}) and velocity dispersion (σ) using this relation:

$$\log \dot{m} = -36.977 + \log L_{bol} - 4.02 \log \sigma \quad (1)$$

The log distributions of accretion rates for the Seyfert galaxies are shown in figures 1.1 – 1.3. Accretion rate distributions for all the Seyfert galaxies show a mean log of -2.101 (accretion rate, $\dot{m} = 0.0079$) with standard deviation 1.089 as shown in figure 3.3a. The Seyfert 1s and 2s (figures 1.2 and 1.3) have the mean log of their accretion rate as -1.884 ($\dot{m} = 0.0131$) and -3.508 ($\dot{m} = 0.0003146$) with standard deviations 0.9127 and 1.092 respectively. An assessment of the log distributions of accretion rates for Seyfert 1s and 2s shows that Seyfert 1s have higher accretion rate than those of Seyfert 2s. This is in agreement with the postulate of Elitzur et. al. (2014) that, the decrease in accretion rate is as a result of the increment on the black hole mass and the prediction of the presence of the obscuring torus and BLR disappearance at a low accretion rate.

Fig. 1.1 Distribution of Log of Accretion rate for both Seyfert 1s and 2s

Fig. 1.2 Distribution of Log of Accretion rate for Seyfert 1s

Fig. 1.3 Distribution of Log of Accretion rate for Seyfert 2s

(b). Black Hole Mass: Black holes of stellar masses are expected to form when very massive stars collapse at the end of their life cycle. After a black hole has formed, it can continue to grow by absorbing mass from its surroundings. By absorbing other stars and merging with other black holes, supermassive black holes of millions of solar masses (M_{\odot}) may form. Despite its invisible interior, the presence of a black hole can be extrapolated through its interaction with other matter and with electromagnetic radiation such as light. Matter falling onto a black hole can form an accretion disk heated by friction, forming some of the brightest objects in the universe. If there are other stars orbiting a black hole, their orbit can be used to determine the mass and location of the black hole.

Using the M–sigma ($M-\sigma$) relation, the mass of the supermassive black hole can be estimated as;

$$M_{BH} = 10^8 M_{\odot} \times 3.1(\sigma/200\text{kms}^{-1})^4 \quad (2)$$

where; M_{BH} is the black hole mass, M_{\odot} is the solar mass and σ is the velocity dispersion. The log distributions of black hole mass for the Seyfert galaxies are shown in figures 2.1 – 2.3. Black hole mass distributions for all the Seyfert galaxies show a mean log of 8.486 ($M_{BH} = 3.062 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$) with log of standard deviation 0.6022 as shown in figure 3.4a. The Seyfert 1s and 2s (figures 2.2 and 2.3) have mean of their log of black hole mass as 8.395 ($M_{BH} = 2.483 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$) and 9.078 ($M_{BH} = 1.197 \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$) with log of standard deviations 0.5606 and 0.5230 respectively. A review of the log distributions of black hole mass for Seyfert 1s and 2s shows that Seyfert 2s are more massive than the Seyfert 1s.

Fig. 2.1 Distribution of Log of Black Hole Mass for both Seyfert 1s and 2s

Fig. 2.2 Distribution of Log of Black Hole Mass for Seyfert 1s

Fig. 2.3 Distribution of Log of Black Hole Mass for Seyfert 2s

Table 1 shows distribution statistics for the parameters and Table 2 is the correlation values for all the Seyfert galaxies (S_{ALL}) (217,272 galaxies), the Seyfert 1 galaxies (S1s) (188,486 galaxies) and the Seyfert 2 galaxies (S2s) (28,786 galaxies).

Table 1 Distribution of Parameters for the Seyfert Galaxies

Parameters	Mean			Standard Deviation		
	S_{ALL}	S1s	S2s	S_{ALL}	S1s	S2s
\dot{m}	0.0079	0.0131	0.000315	1.089	0.9127	1.092
$\text{Log } M_{BH}$	8.486	8.395	9.078	0.6022	0.5606	0.5230

Table 2 Correlations of Parameters for the Seyfert Galaxies

Variables	S _{ALL}	S1s	S2s
\dot{m} and L_{bol}	0.042	0.051	0.383
EW_H α and \dot{m}	0.024	0.036	0.155
EW_H α and M_{BH}	0.003	0.005	0.098

These results show that, as the black hole mass of an AGN (Seyfert galaxy) increases, there is a decrease in its accretion rate and the region of broad line emission progressively declines from its high intensity in Seyfert 1s to the point of disappearance. It is possible that intrinsic broad line emission from Seyfert galaxies may follow an evolutionary trend from Seyfert 1 to Seyfert 2 as accretion onto the supermassive black hole is decreasing. Galaxies at their early stage in life are very luminous and accrete matter at a very high rate, but as they get older their luminosities and accretion rate reduce with an associated increment in their black hole masses. These features (low bolometric luminosity, low accretion rate and massive black hole) are mainly associated with the Seyfert 2 galaxies. And since this can only be achieved with time, we posit that there is a possible evolutionary sequence amongst the Seyfert galaxies in which Seyfert 1 galaxies evolve to Seyfert 2 galaxies.

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